

Zinc (II) Complexes with Substituted Pyridines

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As a part of a series of investigations on several d¹⁰ metal complexes, we have now studied some divalent zinc complexes with nitrogen ligands. The complexes of zinc halides with γ -picoline were known long back and the ligand was purified¹ by forming a complex with zinc halides and then distilling it. Detailed studies were, however, not reported. In this communication, we report some complexes obtained by reacting zinc halides with substituted pyridines -viz., β - and γ -picolines and 4-vinyl pyridine.

All the materials used are of pure quality. An ethanolic solution of zinc halide was treated with an ethanolic solution of aliquot amount of β or γ -picoline. With 4-vinyl pyridine, the reaction was carried out in diethyl ether medium. On shaking, solid compounds separated out which were suction filtered and dried *in vacuo*. Similar attempts with α -picoline and 2:6 lutidine were not successful.

The purity of the isolated compounds was established by estimating the metal and the halogen by standard methods. The conductance measurements were carried out using a Toshniwal Conductivity Bridge type CLO102 and a dip-type cell. The relevant analytical and conductance data are recorded in table I.

TABLE I

Analysis, M.P. and conductance of Zn (II) complexes with substituted pyridines.

Compound	Colour & form	M.P.°C	%Metal		%Halogen		ΔM (mbos)	
			Found	Reqd.	Found	Reqd.	(in acetone)	
1. Dichloro bis-(β -picoline) Zinc (II)	White Amorphous	170°	20.09	20.18	21.85	22.05	1.6	
2. Dibromo bis-(β -picoline) Zinc (II)	White Amorphous	180°	15.37	15.81	38.65	38.93	2.4	
3. Dichloro bis-(γ -picoline) Zinc (II)	White Amorphous	176°	20.11	20.18	21.95	22.05	4.7	
4. Dibromo bis-(γ -picoline) Zinc (II)	White Amorphous	168°	15.20	15.81	38.58	38.93	5.1	
5. Dichloro bis (4-vinyl pyridine) Zinc (II)	Yellow Crystalline	110°	18.69	18.78	21.08	20.52	7.8	
6. Dibromo bis- (4-vinyl pyridine) Zinc (II)	Light yellow Crystalline	122°	19.97	14.09	36.69	36.78	4.5	

Magnetic susceptibility measurements were made over solid specimens using Gouy method and all the complexes were found to be diamagnetic. The infra-red absorption spectra were recorded on Nujol mulls using a Unicam SP200 double beam spectrophotometer and the absorption bands in the region 5000-650 cm^{-1} are reported in table II.

TABLE II

Infra-red absorption bands (cm^{-1}) in Nujol mulls of Zinc (II) complexes with substituted pyridines.

L	L= β -picoline		L= γ -picoline			L=4-vinyl pyridine		
	ZnL ₂ Cl ₂	ZnL ₂ Br ₂	L	ZnL ₂ Cl ₂	ZnL ₂ Br ₂	L	ZnL ₂ Cl ₂	ZnL ₂ Br ₂
725(s)	718(vs)	720(s)	742(s)	740(s)	740(s)	808(s)	825(s)	825(s)
	730(sh)	740(w)	823(s)	835(s)	833(vs)	852(vs)	870(vs)	868(vs)
808(s)	810(vs)	815(s)				950(s)	970(s)	970(s)
	840(sh)		1015(vs)	1055(vs)	1050(vs)	1010(vs)	1015(s)	1010(s)
	900(vs)	905(s)	1060(m)	1082(s)	1080(s)		1040(s)	1040(s)
							1050(sh)	1050(sh)
1042(s)	1065(vs)	1070(vs)	1235(s)	1225(s)	1220(w)			
				1240(w)	1240(w)	1081(w)	1090(s)	1082(vs)
1120(w)	1105(m)	1110(m)	1430(w)	—	—	1230(m)	1240(s)	1218(w)
1138(w)	1140(s)	1140(w)	1460(w)	—	—	1245(m)		1238(s)
								1250(sh)
1200(s)	1205(s)	1210(w)	1610(vs)	1635(vs)	1633(vs)	1422(vs)	1430(sh)	1430(vw)
1420(s)	—	—					1450(sh)	1450(sh)
1485(s)	—	—					1470(sh)	1470(sh)
1580(s)	1585(w)							
	1615(s)	1620(w)				1508(s)	1520(sh)	1520(sh)
						1558(s)	1560(vw)	1560(vw)
						1600(vs)	1625(vs)	1625(vs)

s-sharp, vs-very sharp, m-medium, w-weak, vw-very weak, sh-shoulder, — means overlap of Nujol peaks.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Divalent zinc ion has a completely filled $3d^{10}$ non-bonding shell. Hence four coordinated tetrahedral complexes can be formed involving the use of sp^3 hybrid orbitals for bonding. Several such compounds were reported² in the literature. The tetrahalo complexes reported³ by us earlier also belong to the same category. All the compounds reported now (table I) are fairly soluble in acetone and alcohol and have low melting points suggestive of covalent bond formation. The molar conductance, ΛM , values in acetone are very low and indicate that the compounds are not ionic since the value for 1 : 1 electrolytes is round about 150 mhos. All the compounds are diamagnetic as expected for a completely filled non-bonding shell.

Since the ligand is not free but bonded to the metal, nearly all the ligand absorption bands (table II) are split and/or shifted to a shorter wavelength or a higher frequency region. This is expected in case of complexes due to change in bond order consequent to the metal-ligand bonding. Direct metal-ligand stretching frequencies could not be recorded since they are beyond the range of the spectrophotometer used. In this connection, it

2. Bailar, J. C. (Ed.), "Chemistry of Coordination Compounds", Reinhold Publishing Corp., 1956 Ed. p. 373.

3. Dash, K. C. and Ramana Rao, D. V., *J. Ind. Chem. Soc.*, 1964, 41, 600.

may be pointed out that very recently, infra-red spectral studies of metal pyridine, substituted pyridine and quinoline complexes in the region $667-150\text{ cm}^{-1}$ were made by Frank and Rogers⁴ to obtain direct evidence of metal-ligand bonding.

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4. Frank, C. W. and Rogers, L. B., *Inorg. Chem.*, 1966, 5(4), 615 (*C.A.*, 1966, 15185)